

PREVALENCE AND MOLECULAR DETECTION OF *MYCOBACTERIUM TUBERCULOSIS* AND THEIR RESISTANCE TO RIFAMPICIN

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Abstract:

Tuberculosis (TB), caused by the ancient pathogen *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, remains a major global health challenge, with Pakistan ranking fifth among the 22 countries experiencing generalized TB epidemics. Rifampicin (RIF) has long been the cornerstone of TB treatment due to its potent anti-infective properties. This study, conducted in the Abbottabad district from October 2023 to May 2024, aimed to assess the prevalence of TB and rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis, along with identifying key risk factors contributing to the spread of the disease.

A total of 1,370 samples were collected from patients at the Tuberculosis Centre (TBC) and Ayub Medical Complex (AMC), and analyzed using the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay. Samples were treated with a sample mixture at a ratio of 2:1 and incubated for 10 minutes at room temperature. A 2-ml aliquot was then processed using the GeneXpert system for DNA extraction, amplification, and molecular detection of *M. tuberculosis*, as well as identification of rifampicin resistance through polymerase chain reaction (PCR)-based gene mutation sequencing. Of the total subjects, 635 were patients and 745 served as controls over an eight-month period.

Our findings indicate that females were disproportionately affected, with an odds ratio (OR) of 1.12 (0.90-1.38). The highest prevalence was observed in individuals aged 18-40. Significant associations were found between TB and both family sizes greater than five (OR = 1.08, 95% CI: 0.87–1.35) and marital status (OR = 1.57, 95% CI: 1.18–2.08). Illiteracy also demonstrated a significant correlation with TB, supported by a p-value of 0.04. Notably, rural residents exhibited a higher prevalence of TB (OR = 1.29, 95% CI: 1.03–1.62). Pulmonary TB was more prevalent than extrapulmonary TB, with an OR of 1.06 (0.84–1.32).

Underlying health conditions such as diabetes (OR = 1.45, 95% CI: 1.17–1.79) and HIV/AIDS (OR = 2.96, 95% CI: 0.85–15.08) showed significant associations with TB incidence. Smoking also displayed a notable correlation, with an OR of 1.03 (0.82-1.31). Of the detected TB cases, 1.25% (8 patients) were found to be rifampicin-resistant, a statistically significant finding (p-value = 0.002). Among all cases, 573 (90.2%) were new TB patients, while 62 (9.8%) were relapsed cases. The overall detection rate for *M. tuberculosis* was 46.3%, with rifampicin resistance at 1.25%, highlighting the rising threat of drug-resistant TB in the Abbottabad district.

Keywords: *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, TB prevalence, rifampicin resistance, risk factors, drug-resistant tuberculosis, Pakistan

1-Introduction

Tuberculosis (TB) is a chronic, infectious disease that primarily affects the lungs but can spread to other organs, posing a significant public health threat worldwide. The causative agent of TB, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB), was first identified by Robert Koch in 1882. This pathogen remains one of the deadliest bacterial diseases globally, particularly in developing countries where it spreads through the inhalation of respiratory droplets from infected individuals. Despite advancements in medical treatments, TB continues to cause substantial morbidity and mortality, driven in part by the rise of drug-resistant strains and its association with immunocompromised populations, such as those with HIV/AIDS. In addition, factors such as poor living conditions, malnutrition, and limited access to healthcare exacerbate the spread of the disease, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (World Health Organization, 2023).

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is a slow-growing, aerobic, non-motile bacillus that belongs to the *Mycobacteriaceae* family. Its distinguishing characteristic is a complex, waxy cell wall, which makes it highly resistant to desiccation and many common antibiotics. This bacterium has the unique ability to survive within macrophages, evading the host's immune response by inhibiting the fusion of phagosomes and lysosomes. There are several types of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex (MTBC), including *M. tuberculosis*, *M. bovis*, *M. africanum*, and *M. microti*, each varying slightly in their host specificity and geographic distribution. *M. tuberculosis* is the most common and pathogenic species in humans, whereas *M. bovis* primarily affects cattle but can also infect humans through unpasteurized dairy products (Gagneux, 2018).

Tuberculosis (TB) is a highly infectious disease primarily caused by the bacterium *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. It exists in two main forms: pulmonary and extrapulmonary tuberculosis. Pulmonary tuberculosis, the most common form, affects the lungs and is transmitted through airborne droplets. Upon inhalation, the bacteria settle in the alveoli, leading to an immune response that can either control the infection or allow it to progress. The host's immune system forms granulomas, attempting to contain the bacteria, but in cases of active TB, the bacteria multiply, causing lung damage, persistent cough, and hemoptysis. This form of TB is particularly contagious, making it a global public health concern, especially in low-resource settings (World Health Organization, 2020).

Extrapulmonary tuberculosis occurs when *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* spreads from the lungs to other parts of the body, such as the lymph nodes, bones, or central nervous system. This form of TB is more common in immunocompromised individuals, such as those with HIV/AIDS. The mechanisms of infection involve the bacteria escaping the primary site in the lungs, traveling through the bloodstream or lymphatic system to infect other tissues. Clinical manifestations of extrapulmonary TB vary depending on the organ involved, making diagnosis more complex

compared to pulmonary TB. Although less contagious, it is equally dangerous and can lead to severe complications if left untreated (Pai, Behr, & Dowdy, 2016)

Tuberculosis (TB), caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, is primarily transmitted through airborne particles expelled by individuals with active pulmonary TB. When an infected person coughs, sneezes, or even talks, they release microscopic droplets containing the bacteria into the air, which can be inhaled by others. The bacteria typically settle in the lungs, but they can spread through the bloodstream to other parts of the body. Factors such as prolonged exposure to an infected person, overcrowded living conditions, and immunocompromised states significantly increase the risk of TB transmission (WHO, 2021).

The diagnosis of TB involves several clinical and laboratory methods, aimed at detecting either the presence of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* or the immune response to the pathogen. The most common diagnostic tool is the tuberculin skin test (TST), where a small amount of purified protein derivative (PPD) is injected under the skin to observe any reaction indicating prior exposure. More specific tests include the interferon-gamma release assays (IGRAs), which measure the immune response to TB antigens. In cases of active TB, sputum smear microscopy, culture, and nucleic acid amplification tests (NAAT) are utilized to directly identify the bacteria in respiratory secretions (Lawn & Zumla, 2016).

Treatment of TB requires a prolonged course of multiple antibiotics to ensure complete eradication of the bacteria and prevent drug resistance. The standard treatment for drug-susceptible TB is a six-month regimen consisting of four first-line drugs: isoniazid, rifampicin, ethambutol, and pyrazinamide. For multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB), treatment is more complex, involving second-line drugs and potentially extending to 18-24 months. Directly observed therapy (DOT) is often recommended to ensure adherence to the treatment plan, which is crucial for both individual recovery and public health efforts to control TB transmission (Nahid et al., 2019).

Rifampicin is a first-line antibiotic used in the treatment of tuberculosis (TB) due to its ability to inhibit the bacterial DNA-dependent RNA polymerase. This inhibition prevents the transcription process in *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, effectively hindering bacterial replication. Rifampicin's bactericidal activity is crucial for both the initial and continuation phases of TB treatment, making it a cornerstone of anti-tubercular therapy. However, resistance to Rifampicin has emerged as a significant concern in global TB management, often complicating treatment outcomes and leading to higher mortality rates. Resistance typically results from mutations in the *rpoB* gene, which encodes the RNA polymerase beta subunit, altering the target of Rifampicin and diminishing its efficacy (Hu et al., 2019).

Rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RR-TB) is a major public health challenge, frequently occurring as part of multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB). MDR-TB is characterized by resistance to at least Rifampicin and Isoniazid, another first-line drug. The rise of MDR-TB is largely attributed to the misuse or improper management of TB treatment, including incomplete adherence to therapy and incorrect dosing. The World Health Organization (WHO) has noted an alarming increase in RR-TB cases worldwide, necessitating more complex and prolonged

treatment regimens, often involving second-line drugs that are more toxic and less effective than first-line therapies (World Health Organization, 2020).

The molecular mechanism underlying Rifampicin resistance primarily involves mutations in the *rpoB* gene, specifically within an 81-base-pair region known as the Rifampicin Resistance Determining Region (RRDR). These mutations reduce the binding affinity of Rifampicin to the RNA polymerase, allowing the bacteria to continue RNA synthesis despite the presence of the drug. The most common mutations include substitutions at codons 531, 526, and 516 of the *rpoB* gene. These genetic changes are often detectable through molecular diagnostic tools such as the GeneXpert MTB/RIF assay, which facilitates the rapid identification of RR-TB, enabling timely interventions (Campbell et al., 2017).

Multidrug-resistant tuberculosis and Rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis have serious implications for public health, particularly in countries with high TB burdens. Patients with RR-TB or MDR-TB require longer, more expensive treatment regimens, which are associated with higher rates of adverse effects and lower success rates. In addition, the emergence of extensively drug-resistant TB (XDR-TB), which is resistant to both first- and second-line drugs, underscores the urgent need for new treatment strategies and more effective public health interventions. Addressing this growing threat requires a multifaceted approach, including strengthening TB control programs, improving diagnostic capabilities, and investing in research for novel therapeutics (Dheda et al., 2018)

2-Objectives:

- To determine the prevalence of tuberculosis and the frequency of rifampicin-resistance strain in district Abbottabad.
- To determine the risk factors associated with tuberculosis in District Abbottabad.

3-MATERIAL & MATERIALS:

3.1 Ethical Approval

The study protocol received formal approval from the Ethical Committee of the Department of Zoology, Hazara University, Mansehra, Pakistan.

3.2 Study Area

This research was conducted in District Abbottabad, located in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province of Pakistan. Abbottabad is a key district within the Hazara Division, spanning a total area of 1,969 square kilometers, with the city of Abbottabad serving as its central hub. The district is subdivided into three tehsils: Abbottabad, Havelian, and Lower Tanawal, also known as Sherwan. In addition, there is one designated urban administration area, Nawanshahr. Abbottabad district comprises 51 union councils, of which 38 fall under Tehsil Abbottabad and

13 under Tehsil Havelian

Map of district Abbottabad

Please scroll down for 2:

Map of District Abbottabad

3.3 Study Design

This case-control study was conducted at Ayub Medical Complex (AMC) and the District Tuberculosis Control Center (TBC) in Abbottabad from October 2023 to May 2024. A total of 1,370 samples were collected from patients referred to AMC and TBC during the study period.

3.4 Study Population

The study population included individuals of all age groups, ranging from one to one hundred years old, covering both males and females. Demographic factors such as marital status, residential area, family size, and history of previous tuberculosis (TB) treatment were also considered in the study.

3.5 Study Variables

The study analyzed two types of variables:

3.5.1 Independent Variables

Independent variables included demographic factors such as gender, age, area, and family size.

3.5.2 Dependent Variables

Dependent variables focused on health-related factors, including smoking, diabetes mellitus, and other comorbidities such as HIV/AIDS.

3.6 Data Collection

A structured and pretested questionnaire was utilized to collect data. A single observer was responsible for visiting the hospitals, where demographic information was gathered through face-to-face interviews with patients.

3.6.1 Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria for Data Collection

Data were exclusively collected from residents of District Abbottabad. Patients outside of this geographical area were excluded. Furthermore, individuals infected with non-tuberculous Mycobacteria (NTM) or Mycobacterium other than tuberculosis (MOTT) were also excluded from the data collection process.

3.7 Sample Collection

The study involved the collection of 1,370 samples, comprising both pulmonary and extra-pulmonary specimens. Pulmonary samples were obtained through freshly expectorated, uncontaminated sputum, while extra-pulmonary samples included cerebrospinal fluid, ascetic fluid, bone biopsy, pus, lymph fluid, and skin biopsy. For this study, 2-4 mL of each sample was collected into sterile, screw-capped plastic bottles, and labeled with the patient's name and identification number.

3.7.1 Sample Preparation

The sample preparation process involved mixing sodium hydroxide and isopropanol into the sample at a 2:1 ratio.

3.7.2 Liquefaction of the Sample

Samples were vigorously shaken 10–20 times and then incubated at room temperature for 15 minutes. The shaking process was repeated between the 5th and 10th minutes of incubation to ensure the samples were fully liquefied and free from sputum clumps. A sterile transfer pipette was used to transfer a 2 mL liquid sample into the cartridge, which was then loaded into the GeneXpert machine.

3.7.3 PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction)

DNA from the Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) was automatically extracted, amplified, and analyzed using specific forward and reverse primers, as well as probes, to identify TB bacteria and any resistance to Rifampicin. Upon completion of the process, the GeneXpert machine provided the following results:

1. MTB Detected / Rifampicin Resistance Not Detected
2. MTB Detected / Rifampicin Resistance Detected
3. MTB Not Detected

3.8 Data Analysis

The collected data were analyzed using statistical techniques. Descriptive statistics were used to compute frequencies, means, and standard deviations. The strength of associations between variables was assessed using chi-square tests, logistic regression (LR), and odds ratios (OR), with a 95% confidence interval. The data analysis was performed using SPSS software to identify relationships between risk factors.

4- RESULTS:

The current study was conducted in Abbottabad District to assess the prevalence of tuberculosis (TB) and Rifampicin-resistant TB (RIF-resistant TB), as well as to identify the major risk factors associated with TB. A total of 1,370 samples were examined using the GeneXpert technology. Out of 635 TB patients, 355 were females and 280 were males, while the control group of 735 individuals included 345 males and 390 females. Rifampicin resistance was detected in eight patients, comprising three females and five males. The overall prevalence of TB in the present study was found to be 46.35%. Additionally, the data indicated that females exhibited a higher prevalence of TB compared to males. Several key variables, including age, gender, marital status, family size, history of TB treatment, disease site, diabetes, and HIV status, were recorded as part of the disease parameters.

4.1 Analysis of Clinical and Biochemical Data

To investigate potential associations between TB risk factors, clinical and biochemical data, encompassing sociodemographic variables and clinical features, were meticulously analyzed using SPSS software. The descriptive characteristics of the 635 TB patients and 735 controls are outlined in Table 4.1. The analysis provided a comprehensive comparison of these groups, shedding light on the disparities in disease occurrence and risk factors.

The mean age of TB patients was found to be 36.96 ± 20.6 years, ranging from 1 to 99 years, whereas the mean age of the control group was slightly higher, at 42.08 ± 19.1 years, with a range from 1 to 90 years. Other significant variables, including gender, family size, and disease site, revealed means of 0.56 ± 0.497 , 0.59 ± 0.492 , and 0.66 ± 0.473 for the TB patients, respectively. In contrast, the control group had means of 0.53 ± 0.499 for gender, 0.61 ± 0.488 for family size, and 0.68 ± 0.468 for disease site. These findings provide insights into the demographic and clinical profiles of TB patients and help in understanding the distribution of the disease across different population segments.

Table 4.1: Sociodemographic variables and clinical feature of the cases control sample population

Variable	Category	Control (%)	Mean	SD	Range	Cases (%)	Mean	SD	Range
Gender	Male	345(46.9)	0.53	0.499	0-1	280(44.1)	0.56	0.497	0-1
	Female	390(53.1)				355(55.9)			
Age	Infant (1-1.5)	11(1.5)	42.08	19.125	1-90	11(1.7)	36.39	20.67	1-99
	Toddler (1.5-3)	12(1.6)				10(1.6)			
	Pre-school (3-5)	7(1.0)				7(1.1)			
	Early School (5-12)	33(4.5)				9(3.0)			
	Adolescence (12-18)	33(4.5)				59(9.3)			
	Young Adult (18-40)	247(33.6)				292(46.0)			
	Middle Adult (40-65)	315(42.9)				166(26.1)			
	Late Adult (>65)	77 (10.5)				71(11.2)			
Family Size	<5	285(38.8)	0.61	0.488	0-1	259(40.8)	0.59	0.492	0-1
	>5	450(61.2)				376(59.2)			
Mode	Pulmonary	498(67.8)	0.68	0.468	0-1	422(66.5)	0.66	0.473	0-1
	Extra Pulmonary	237(32.2)				213(33.5)			
Marital Status	Married	630(55.5)				503(79.2)			
	Unmarried	105(14.3)				132(20.8)			
Area	Rural	517(70.3)				411(64.7)			
	Urban	218(29.7)				224(35.3)			
History of TB treatm	New	5(0.7)				573(90.2)			
	Relapse	0(0)				62(9.8)			
	Nil	730(99.3)							

ent				0(0)	
Rif-Resistance	Detected	0(0)		8(1.3)	
	Not Detected	735(100)		627(98.7)	
Sample Type	Ascetic	49(6.7)		47(7.4)	
	Bone biopsy	14(1.9)		11(1.7)	
	CSF	29(3.9)		19(3.0)	
	Lymph fluid	54(7.3)		47(7.4)	
	Pleural fluid	72(9.8)		79(12.4)	
	Pus	9(1.2)		4(0.6)	
	Skin biopsy	11(1.5)		69(0.9)	
	Sputum	497(67.7)		422(66.5)	
Educational level	Educated	233(31.7)		234(36.9)	
	Un-Educated	502(68.3)		401(63.1)	
Covid Vaccination	Vaccinated	719(97.8)		611(96.2)	
	Non-Vaccinated	16(2.2)		24(3.8)	
Diabetics	Diabetic	372(50.6)		263(41.4)	
	Non-Diabetic	363(49.4)		372(58.6)	
Smoking	Smoker	530(72.1)		453(71.3)	
	Non-Smoker	205(27.9)		182(28.7)	

4.2 Prevalence of tuberculosis

The current study was carried out in the Abbottabad district, in which a total of 1370 samples were tested, of which 635 were patients and 735 were controls. In the total of 635 positive patients, 355 were female and 280 were male, among whom rifampicin resistance was detected in 3 females and 5 males, respectively. And among healthy people, 345 were male and 390 were female. A high frequency is recorded in the age group 18 to 40 (46%). We also found out the area-wise prevalence of TB in Abbottabad district. Parameters of the disease like age, gender, marital status, family size, TB treatment history, disease site, diabetes, and HIV status were recorded (Table 4.2).

4.3 Prevalence RIF-Resistance tuberculosis

Eight of the 635 *M. tuberculosis* patients tested positive for rifampicin resistance. Males had 5 (62.5%) and females had 3 (37.5%) rifampicin-resistant *M. tuberculosis*, respectively. Sputum samples were strongly related to rifampicin-resistant TB (100%). Rifampicin resistance was found in 8 (100%) of the pulmonary cases and 0 (0%) of the extra-pulmonary cases. Six (75%) cases of rifampicin resistance were noticed in all patients with MTB and diabetes co-infected. In 8 rifampicin-positive cases, 6 (75%) were relapse and 2 (25%) were new cases. Six (75%) cases of rifampicin resistance were noticed in all patients with MTB/AIDs co-infection (Table 4.3).

Table 4.2: Prevalence of *M. tuberculosis* patients in Abbottabad (N =635)

Variables	Category	Total TB Cases	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	280	44.1
	Female	355	55.9
Area	Urban	224	35.3
	Rural	411	64.7
Family size	<5	259	40.8
	>5	376	59.2
Marital Status	Married	503	79.2
	Un Married	132	20.8
Age	Infant (1-1.5)	11	1.7
	Toddler (1.5-3)	10	1.6
	Pre-school (3-5)	7	1.1
	Early School (5-12)	9	3.0
	Adolescence (12-18)	59	9.3
	Young Adult (18-40)	292	46.0
	Middle Adult (40-65)	166	26.1
	Late Adult(>65)	71	11.2
Sample type	Ascetic	47	7.4
	Bone biopsy	11	1.7
	CSF	19	3.0
	Lymph fluid	47	7.4
	Pleural fluid	79	12.4

	Pus	4	0.6
	Skin biopsy	6	0.9
	Sputum	422	66.5
Mode	Pulmonary	422	66.5
	Extra-pulmonary	213	33.5
History of TB treatment	New	573	90.2
	Relapse	62	9.8
	Nil	0	0
Covid vaccination	Vaccinated	611	96.2
	Non-vaccinated	24	3.8
Educational level	Educated	234	36.9
	Un-educated	401	63.1
Rifampicin Resistance	Detected	8	1.3
	Not Detected	627	98.7
Aids	Yes	6	0.9
	No	534	84.1
	Unknown	95	15.0

Table 4.3: Prevalence of rifampicin resistant M. tuberculosis in each variable among the total M. tuberculosis cases

Variables	Category	Cases (%)	Controls (%)
Gender	Male	5(62.5)	620(4.5)
	Female	3(37.5)	742(54.5)
Area	Rural	7(87.5)	921(67.6)
	Urban	1(12.5)	441(32.4)
Family size	>5	6(75)	820(60.2)
	<5	2 (25)	542(39.8)
Age	Infant	0	22(1.6)
	Toddler	0	22(1.6)
	Pre-school	0	14(1.0)
	Early-school	0	52(3.8)
	Adolescence	1(12.5)	91(6.7)
	Young-Adult	5(62.5)	476(34.9)
	Middle-Adult	2(25.0)	537(39.4)

	Late-Adult	0	148(10.9)
Marital Status	Married	6(75)	1127(82.7)
	Un-Married	2(25)	235(17.3)
Sample type	Ascetic	0	96(7.0)
	Bone-biopsy	0	25(1.8)
	CSF	0	48(3.5)
	Lymph node	0	101(7.4)
	Pleural fluid	0	151(11.1)
	Pus	0	13(1.0)
	Skin biopsy	0	17(1.2)
	Sputum	8(100)	911(66.9)
Mode	Pulmonary	8(100)	912(67.3)
	Extra-pulmonary	0	450(32.8)
Educational level	Educated	3(37.5)	464(34.1)
	Un-educated	5(62.5)	898(65.9)
Diabetes	Diabetic	6(75)	629(46.2)
	Non-diabetic	2(25)	733(53.8)
Smoking	Yes	2(25)	385(28.3)
	No	6(75)	977(71.7)
Covid-Vaccination	Vaccinated	7(87.5)	1323(97.1)
	Non-vaccinated	1(12.5)	39(2.9)
History of previous TB treatment	New	2(25)	575(42.2)
	Relapse	6(75)	56(4.1)
	Nil	0	731(53.7)
Aids	Yes	6(75)	8(0.6)
	No	2(25)	187(13.7)
	Unknown	0	1167(85.7)

4.4 Gender-wise Prevalence of Tuberculosis

In the present study, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (MTB) was detected in 280 (44.1%) out of the 635 male specimens and in 355 (55.9%) of the female specimens. This data highlights a higher prevalence of tuberculosis among females compared to males. Furthermore, out of the total 8 cases of Rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RIF-resistant TB), 5 cases (62.5%) were identified in males, while 3 cases (37.5%) were detected in females. These findings suggest that, although the overall prevalence of tuberculosis was higher among females, the occurrence of Rifampicin-

resistant strains impacted both genders, with no significant skew towards one gender in terms of resistance. This equal distribution of resistance indicates the need for gender-neutral strategies in tackling RIF-resistant TB.

Figure 4.1: Gender wise prevalence of tuberculosis

4.5 MTB and RIF-Resistance in Various Age Groups

Patients were categorized into eight distinct age groups: 1-1.5, 1.5-3, 3-5, 5-12, 12-18, 18-40, 40-65, and >65 years, to assess the prevalence of MTB and Rifampicin-resistant tuberculosis (RIF-resistant TB) across different age ranges. The age distribution revealed that the majority of both MTB and RIF-resistant cases were concentrated within the 18-40 age group. This suggests that young adults and middle-aged individuals are more susceptible to contracting tuberculosis, as well as developing resistance to Rifampicin. These findings underline the importance of focusing public health interventions and awareness programs on this age group to curb the spread of both tuberculosis and drug-resistant strains.

Figure 4.2: Distribution of data based on Age

4.6 Association of Risk Factors with Tuberculosis

4.6.1 Association of Gender with Tuberculosis

Data were meticulously collected from both male and female participants, revealing a mean age of 0.56 ± 0.497 for patients and a mean age of 0.53 ± 0.499 for controls (refer to Table 4.1). The analysis indicated that females are more susceptible to tuberculosis, primarily due to barriers in accessing TB services. Cultural factors often lead to male family members being unwilling to facilitate healthcare for their female counterparts, thereby compromising their health. The data demonstrated a pronounced prevalence of the disease among females, establishing a strong association with tuberculosis, evidenced by an odds ratio (OR) of 1.12 (0.90-1.38) and a P-value of 0.29. This underscores the need for targeted interventions that address gender-specific barriers to healthcare access.

4.6.2 Association of Age with Tuberculosis

The study encompassed individuals across all age groups, as tuberculosis is inherently age-dependent, with susceptibility varying according to lifestyle and environmental factors. The mean age of tuberculosis patients was 36.96 ± 20.6 years, spanning from 1 to 99 years, while the mean age of the control group was 42.08 ± 19 years, ranging from 1 to 90 years. Age was categorized into eight distinct groups: infants (11 patients and 11 controls), toddlers (10 patients and 12 controls), preschoolers (7 patients and 7 controls), early school-age children (19 patients

and 33 controls), adolescents (59 patients and 33 controls), young adults (292 patients and 247 controls), middle adults (166 patients and 315 controls), and late adults (71 patients and 77 controls). A significant association was identified within the young adult category, which exhibited a heightened risk of tuberculosis, with an odds ratio of 1.93 (1.13–3.30) and a P-value of 0.01. This finding suggests that young adults are particularly vulnerable to developing tuberculosis, highlighting the necessity for targeted public health strategies aimed at this demographic.

Age	Age Categories	OR (CI95%)	P
1-1.5	Infant	A	
1.5-3	Toddler	1.08(0.44-2.6)	0.85
3-5	Pre-School	0.90(0.36-2.22)	0.82
5-12	Early-School	1.08(0.30-3.24)	0.88
12-18	Adolescence	0.66(0.32-1.19)	0.15
18-40	Young-Adult	1.93(1.13-3.30)	0.01
40-65	Middle-Adult	1.28(0.89-1.84)	0.18
>65	Late-Adult	0.57(0.39-0.83)	0.003

Table 4.3: Association of age with tuberculosis

4.6.3 Association of Family Size with Tuberculosis

The study investigated the relationship between family size and the prevalence of tuberculosis by categorizing families into two groups: those with fewer than five members and those with more than five. Among families comprising five or fewer individuals, there were 259 patients and 285 controls; conversely, families with more than five members accounted for 376 patients and 450 controls. Notably, among the cases of Rifampicin resistance, six patients hailed from larger families (>5 members), while only two patients were from smaller families (<5 members). The analysis revealed a significant association between larger family sizes and tuberculosis, with an odds ratio (OR) of 1.08 (0.87-1.35). This suggests that individuals residing in larger family units may face an elevated risk of contracting tuberculosis, underscoring the need for public health initiatives that address the dynamics of household size in relation to disease transmission.

Figure 4.3: Association of family size with tuberculosis

4.6.4 Association of prevalent area with tuberculosis

Tuberculosis is a transmittable disease that is transmitted from place to place and person to person. Rural areas show a significant association with tuberculosis, with an OR of 1.29 (1.03–1.62) and a P-value of 0.02.

Figure 4.4: Association of prevalent area with tuberculosis

4.6.5 Association of marital status with tuberculosis

In the present study, 503 patients were married and 132 were unmarried, while in the controls, 630 were married and 105 were unmarried. And among RIF-resistant cases, six were married and two were unmarried. Marital status shows a significant association with tuberculosis, with an OR of 1.57 (1.18–2.08) and a P-value of 0.002.

Figure 4.5: Association of marital status with tuberculosis

4.6. Association of disease site and Sample type with tuberculosis

In the present study, both pulmonary and extra-pulmonary samples were included. In pulmonary samples, 422 were patients and 498 were controls. And in Extra-pulmonary samples, 213 were patients and 237 were controls. And among rifampicin resistance cases, 8 were pulmonary, while 0 were extrapulmonary.

In the present study, different samples are detected by GeneXpert, i.e., Ascetic, bone biopsy, CSF, lymph fluid, pleural fluid, pus, skin biopsy, and sputum. Among these samples, sputum has a high association with tuberculosis. Pulmonary sites have a high association with tuberculosis, with an OR of 1.06 (0.84–1.32) and a P-value of 0.61.

Figure 4.6: Association of disease site with tuberculosis

Figure 4.7: Association of sample type with tuberculosis

4.6.7 Association of smoking with tuberculosis

There was a substantial link between smoking and tuberculosis, and smoking increased the mortality rate. In the current study, smoking has a significant association with tuberculosis, with an OR of 1.03(0.82-1.31) and a P-value of 0.75.

4.6.8 Association of Diabetes mellitus and other diseases (HIV) with tuberculosis

Because of their weakened immune systems, people with diabetes and HIV were at a higher risk of developing tuberculosis. Our study included both people who had diabetes along with tuberculosis as well as those who did not. DM was an independent risk factor for tuberculosis (OR = 1.45 (1.17–1.96) P-value 0.001), while other diseases like HIV/AIDS had a strong correlation with TB (OR = 2.96 (0.58–15.08) P-value 0.19) (Table 4.5).

4.6.9 Association of covid vaccine with tuberculosis

Data gathered from October 2022 to May 2023 indicates a relationship between the COVID vaccine and TB. Of the patients, 611 were vaccinated and 24 were not vaccinated. In controls, 719 were vaccinated and 16 were not.

Covid vaccination shows a significant association with tuberculosis, with a P-value of 0.07 (Table 4.5).

4.6.10 Association of education with tuberculosis

Education is associated with tuberculosis. In our present study, 234 patients were educated, while 401 were uneducated. And in the controls, 233 were educated and 502 were un-educated. Educational level shows a significant association with tuberculosis, with a p-value of 0.04 (Table 4.5).

4.6.11 Association of Rif-resistance with tuberculosis

Rifampicin resistance is highly associated with tuberculosis. In the present study, among 635 positive cases of tuberculosis, 8 were resistant to rifampicin. Rifampicin resistance shows a significant association

Figure 4.8: Association of Rif-resistance with tuberculosis

4.6.12 Association of previous history of TB treatment with tuberculosis

A history of previous TB treatment is associated with tuberculosis. In the present study, the history of TB treatment is divided into three categories: new, relapse, and nil. Among patients, there were 573 new cases and 5 controls. In relapse, 62 were patients and 0 were in control. In

the nil category, 0 were patients, and 735 were controls. Previous history of TB treatment shows a significant association, with a P-value of 0.00 (Table 4.5).

Table 4.5: Binary logistic analysis of factors associated with tuberculosis

Risk Factors	OR (95% CI)	P
Gender		
Male	0.89(0.07-1.10)	0.29
Female	1.12(0.90-1.38)	
Family size		0.44
>5	1.08(0.87-1.35)	
<5	0.91(0.74-1.38)	
Area		0.02
Rural	1.29(1.03-1.62)	
Urban	0.77(0.61-0.97)	
Marital Status		0.002
Married	1.57(1.18-2.08)	
Un-Married	0.63(0.47-0.84)	
Disease site		0.61
Pulmonary	1.06(0.84-1.32)	
Extra pulmonary	0.94(0.75-1.18)	
Smoking		0.75
Smoker	1.03(0.82-1.31)	
Non-smoker	0.96(0.76-1.21)	
Diabetes mellitus		0.001
Diabetic	1.45(1.17-1.79)	
Non-Diabetic	0.69(0.55-0.85)	
Aids		
Yes	2.96(0.58-15.08)	
No	0.33(0.06-1.71)	
Unknown	0.27(0.05-1.38)	
Covid vaccination		0.07
Vaccinated	0.567(0.298-1.07)	
Non-vaccinated		
Education		0.04
Educated	0.795(0.63-0.99)	
Un-educated		
Rif-Resistance		0.002
History of previous TB treatment		>0.001

5- Discussion

Tuberculosis (TB) is one of the oldest diseases known to humanity and remains the second leading cause of infection-related mortality worldwide. This case-control study was conducted at Ayub Medical Complex (AMC) and the District TB Control Center (TBC) in Abbottabad from October 2022 to May 2023. A total of 1,370 samples were collected from patients referred to both institutions. Primary data was meticulously gathered using a specialized pro forma, filled out by the participants.

Our findings reveal a notably higher incidence of tuberculosis in females compared to males. Consistent with the observations of Sadaat Ullah et al. (2022), who reported a female incidence rate of 54.16% against 40.42% for males, our study corroborates the notion that females are more susceptible to TB. Similar conclusions were drawn by Iqbal et al. (2022) and Tahseen et al. (2020), with the latter reporting a prevalence of 30.5% in females versus 27.9% in males. Contrarily, some studies (Abdullah, 2022; Iqbal et al., 2022) suggested a higher incidence among males. Our study concluded that males are less affected by tuberculosis than females, with an odds ratio (OR) of 1.12 (0.90-1.38). The observed discrepancies in gender ratios may be attributable to demographic variances across different global regions and within Pakistan.

Age group analysis indicated that individuals aged 18–28 years exhibited a higher susceptibility to rifampicin-resistant pulmonary tuberculosis (RR-PTB). Awais et al. (2018) found that a majority of Mycobacterium tuberculosis (MTB) and rifampicin-resistant cases (63.9% MTB and 10.6% rifampicin resistance) belonged to the 16-30 age bracket. Furthermore, Gautam et al. (2018) noted that 36% of rifampicin-resistant M. tuberculosis cases occurred in individuals aged 20–40 years. Our study identified the young adult demographic (18-40 years) as having the highest prevalence rate of tuberculosis at 46% (OR= 1.93 [1.13-3.30]).

We also observed that family sizes exceeding five members had a significant association with tuberculosis, indicated by an OR of 1.08 (0.87-1.35). Rural patients exhibited a markedly higher incidence rate (64.7%) of TB compared to their urban counterparts, corroborating Iqbal et al. (2022), who reported a prevalence of 90% in rural areas. This finding aligns with previous studies by Hasan et al. (2010), which highlighted that the prevalence of multidrug-resistant TB (MDR-TB) in Pakistan's rural locales is potentially exacerbated by inadequate awareness campaigns, limited access to resources, and poverty.

Marriage status was also a significant factor, with our study revealing a TB prevalence of 79.2% among married individuals (OR= 1.57 [1.18-2.08]) compared to unmarried individuals. This heightened risk may stem from close proximity and interaction, as married couples often share living spaces. Rangaka et al. (2015) posited that married women frequently conceal their illness to avoid stigmatization or abandonment.

In our analysis, both pulmonary and extrapulmonary samples were examined, with pulmonary TB showing a significant association (OR= 1.06 [0.84-1.32]). The prevalence of rifampicin resistance was documented at 1.25% for pulmonary samples and 0% for extrapulmonary samples,

aligning with the findings of Jan et al. (2020). Among sample types, sputum samples constituted 66.5% of pulmonary cases, while pleural fluid represented 12.4% of extrapulmonary TB cases.

Our results align with studies indicating that smoking significantly correlates with *M. tuberculosis* infection. Abdullah et al. (2023) further substantiated this connection, asserting that heavy smoking inflicts direct harm to pulmonary health, thus increasing TB risk.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) emerged as a notable risk factor, with an observed association of OR= 1.45 (1.17-1.79) and $p=0.001$. This finding corroborates existing literature, such as Martinez and Kornfeld (2019), which highlights a DM prevalence exceeding 40% among newly diagnosed TB patients, indicating a substantial interplay between these two conditions.

Moreover, the study identified a significant association between TB and HIV/AIDS, with an OR of 2.96 (0.58–15.08). As noted by Gardezi et al. (2023), TB remains the most common opportunistic infection among HIV-positive individuals. WHO estimates suggest that individuals with HIV are 19 times more likely to develop TB compared to those without the virus.

Educational attainment also surfaced as a critical determinant, with 63.1% of TB patients being uneducated. This trend is consistent with findings from Siddiqui et al. (2011), who reported that a majority of TB patients lacked education, likely contributing to their ignorance about TB transmission, management, and prevention strategies.

Regarding rifampicin resistance, our study reported a significant association ($P=0.002$) in TB cases, with a resistance prevalence of 9.8%. In line with the findings of Mba et al. (2023), a significant proportion of patients (90.2%) were newly diagnosed, with only 9.8% classified as relapse cases. Among rifampicin-resistant patients, two were new cases and six were relapses, highlighting the persistence of TB in this population.

In conclusion, our study underscores the multifaceted nature of tuberculosis epidemiology in Abbottabad, revealing significant associations with gender, age, family size, rural residency, marital status, smoking, diabetes, HIV status, education, and rifampicin resistance. Addressing these determinants is crucial for implementing effective TB control strategies.

6- Conclusion:

Tuberculosis, caused by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, continues to be a significant global health challenge, with a particularly alarming prevalence in Pakistan. Contributing factors to this ongoing epidemic include poor sanitation, inadequate public awareness, and delays in diagnosis, all of which exacerbate the disease's transmission. A recent study conducted in the Abbottabad district underscores this issue, revealing a notably high incidence of tuberculosis, especially among females and individuals aged 18 to 40. Furthermore, the study identified substantial correlations between the disease and variables such as family size, marital status, educational attainment, and residency in rural areas. These findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions, including comprehensive educational initiatives and enhanced healthcare access, to effectively combat the burgeoning tuberculosis crisis in Pakistan. Addressing these socio-

economic determinants is crucial for reducing the burden of tuberculosis and improving public health outcomes in the region.

Recommendations

The high prevalence of tuberculosis in the Abbottabad district, particularly among females, can be primarily attributed to factors such as illiteracy and a lack of awareness regarding the disease. To alleviate the burden of tuberculosis, it is recommended that targeted awareness and screening programs be implemented, with a specific focus on educating individuals, especially those who are illiterate, about the disease, its transmission, and prevention strategies.

Additionally, the rising incidence of resistant strains of tuberculosis within the Pakistani population is a pressing concern, driven by inadequate awareness sessions on transmission and a lack of preventive measures among the general populace. Consequently, both commercial and public healthcare sectors should undertake comprehensive initiatives on a large scale to address these issues. This includes increasing awareness campaigns centered on multidrug-resistant tuberculosis (MDR-TB) transmission, implementing effective preventive measures, and striving to achieve the most substantial reduction in MDR-TB infections possible. By fostering a well-informed public and ensuring the availability of preventive resources, we can significantly combat the tuberculosis epidemic in the region.

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